

Hipparcos Progress Report

L Lindegren, 15 July 1992

For over 2.5 years, since the beginning of December 1989, the ESA Hipparcos satellite has routinely acquired astrometric and photometric data of very high quality. The main observation programme comprises over 118,000 stars in the so-called Input Catalogue (recently published as ESA SP-1136) together with 48 minor planets and the moons Europa, Titan and Iapetus. In addition about one million stars are being observed as part of the so-called Tycho programme.

In spite of the many difficulties caused by the unintended elliptical orbit and the subsequent early pessimistic outlook, the project is now in very good shape and we believe that the original mission goals will be reached and probably surpassed. Technically the satellite may continue to operate until mid-1994, at which time the median accuracy of the positions and parallaxes for the 118,000 stars will be less than 2 milli-arcsec (mas) while the proper motions just reach the 1 mas yr^{-1} level (Figure 1). — Very recently certain technical problems have occurred with the gyroscopes on board the satellite. This has resulted in a significant loss of data during some weeks, but it is too early to assess how serious it will be in the long run. The satellite now continues to collect very good data at a somewhat reduced rate.

Currently the complex data reductions lag behind the observations by more than a year, due to the necessity to iterate the early solutions and the desire to make detailed checks and analyses of the intermediate results. The main verification tool is a series of data comparisons between the two independent 'reduction consortia', FAST and NDAC. Both groups have recently completed a preliminary analysis of the first year of observations. The agreement is excellent and various external checks clearly demonstrate the outstanding quality of these early results.

The determination of the gravitational light deflection at right angle to the sun may illustrate the quality of the solutions. The present estimate, using only one year of data, is $(4.05 \pm 0.03) \text{ mas}$, in complete agreement with the general-relativistic value $2GMc^{-2}/(1 \text{ AU}) = 4.0719 \dots \text{ mas}$.

This report is intended to give a broad impression of the kind of results obtained so far. It is important to remember that the same objects are being observed again and again throughout the mission, and that the reductions of these data are cumulative. What is shown below is therefore not representative of the end results, which will certainly be both better and more plentiful.

Figure 1. Predicted evolution of mission accuracy (median standard errors) with time.

Positions

For most of the programme stars positions (at epoch 1990.5) have been determined in a globally consistent coordinate system and with individual errors in the 2–5 mas range. This is far more accurate than any previous optical positions, and the systematic errors present in all ground-based positional catalogues are very clearly revealed (Figure 2). All current and planned astrometric programmes, e.g., using automatic meridian circles, must take these results into account and will benefit enormously from them.

Parallaxes

The preliminary trigonometric parallaxes, which so far have been calculated for over 80,000 stars, provide the most convincing demonstration of the data quality. Only 10% of the parallaxes are negative, which is consistent with an *external* standard error of about 2.1 mas for the majority of stars (Figure 3). Recalling that this was derived just from the first year of data it appears that the predictions in Figure 1 are quite conservative.

The large-angle measurement technique used with Hipparcos will in principle give *absolute* parallaxes, thus eliminating an annoying error source in ground-based parallaxes (which are always measured relative to presumably distant background stars). This has been confirmed, to within a fraction of a mas, by several independent tests. Figure 4 shows the preliminary Hipparcos parallaxes for all 32 stars in this material believed to be members of the Magellanic Clouds. The distribution is almost perfectly centred on zero — the expected parallax is about 0.02 mas — and the RMS width (2.8 mas) is consistent with the expected accuracy.

An HR diagram constructed for some 3000 stars with parallaxes determined to better than 10% relative accuracy is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 2. Systematic differences between Hipparcos and ground-based positions in the PPM catalogue — currently the best-available practical realisation of the FK5 system. Each vector gives the mean displacement in a $7.5^\circ \times 7.5^\circ$ area.

Figure 3. The observed distribution of 82,309 parallaxes (shown here as a histogram) may be 'explained' by a model distribution of the true parallaxes (dashed curve) convolved with the distribution of observational errors, yielding the solid curve. From this one may infer a mean error of about 2.1 mas for $\frac{3}{4}$ of the data and about 5 mas for the rest.

Figure 4. Observed parallaxes for stars believed to be in the Magellanic Clouds. This and other tests on distant stars demonstrate that the zero-point error in the Hipparcos parallaxes is substantially less than a milli-arcsec.

Figure 5. A colour-magnitude (HR) diagram constructed from preliminary parallaxes for 2927 stars. The relative formal uncertainty of each parallax is less than 10%, corresponding to 0.22 units in absolute magnitude. Note that individual distances are obtained for a sizable number of giants and early main sequence stars. Many of the stars in the diagram have no ground-based photoelectric photometry but had their accurate colours and magnitudes determined for the first time by Hipparcos. The colour index is on the Tycho photometric system, $\approx 1.2 \times (B-V)_{\text{Johnson}}$.

Figure 6. (Left) Example of a variable star discovered with Hipparcos and the fitted light curve. (Right) Magnitude measurements of a photometric standard star, confirmed to be constant to $< 1\%$. (Both diagrams by courtesy of the FAST consortium.)

Photometry

The photometric measurements are an impressive by-product of the Hipparcos mission. Each passage of a programme star across the instrument's field of view provides an accurate estimate of the magnitude in a broad but well-defined wavelength band (H_p). For stars brighter than 10th magnitude, the starmapper detectors additionally provide independent magnitudes in two wavelength bands (B_T , V_T). The estimated accuracy of a single observation (field crossing) is about 0.01 mag for $H_p \leq 7$, 0.02 mag at $H_p = 9$ and 0.07 mag at $H_p = 11$.

Although this accuracy may be modest compared with the best ground-based photometry, there is a tremendous advantage in the number and frequency of observations, the stability of the photometric system and the complete sky coverage with a single instrument. During a few years several tens to hundreds of observations are collected on each object with time intervals ranging from 20 min to a few months. Many of the stars are variable at this level of accuracy, and for some of them light curves can be determined (Figure 6, left). For non-variable stars very accurate mean magnitudes are obtained, often at the milli-magnitude level (Figure 6, right).

Double and multiple stars

Part of the off-line reductions made in Lund concern the double and multiple stars. Although these objects are more complicated to process than single stars, we expect to obtain their astrometric parameters to similar accuracy. In addition, the relative positions and magnitudes of the components are determined (Figure 7).

Conclusions

The Hipparcos mission is producing an abundance of astrometric and photometric data which, despite their preliminary nature, obviously have very great scientific potential. While the final results are still several years ahead, the provisional data will nevertheless soon be available to the scientific community, subject to certain rules and restrictions. Proposals for specific investigations using this material are most welcome.

Figure 7. Example of a close binary ($\rho = 0.2$ arcsec) observed with Hipparcos. The point marked 1990 is the relative position of the secondary as determined by the satellite. The size of the point corresponds to the formal uncertainty of the position. The crosses are speckle-interferometric measurements from the ground.